

SYNTHESIS IN THE 4-AZAFLUORENE GROUP. PART II. SYNTHESIS OF 4-AZAFLUORENES AND 7-AZAFLUORANTHENES

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Synthesis of some 4-azafluorenes from 1-indanone is described. Extension of the methods lead to the synthesis of 7-azafluoranthenes from acenaphthenone.

A general method of synthesis of the 4-azafluorene ring system from 2-phenylpyridine-3-carboxylic acids has been described in an earlier communication (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 371). It appeared desirable, however, to effect a more direct synthesis from indane derivatives. This has been achieved according to the scheme presented below.

2-Hydroxymethylene-1-indanone on treatment with 2-aminocrotonitrile in absolute alcohol afforded the hydroxy compound (I) which on heating was converted into 2-cyano-3-methyl-4-azafluorene (II). This was obtained in a better yield from the related carboxylic acid (IV), obtainable from 1-indanone-2-glyoxylic ester, as shown above. Hydrolysis of the cyano-ester (III) gave 3-methyl-4-azafluorene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid (V), which on decarboxylation afforded 3-methyl-4-azafluorene, identified through the picrate. In an analogous manner, acenaphthenone was converted into the corresponding glyoxylic ester which gave the 7-azafluoranthene (VI: R = CO₂Et) on condensation with 2-aminocrotonitrile.

When 2-aminocrotonitrile was replaced by ethyl 2-aminocrotonate, the outcome was unexpected. With an excess of the ester and 2-hydroxymethylene-1-indanone at the room temperature, the sole product was a light yellow crystalline material (m.p. 166°) for which accurate analytical data were difficult to obtain. The compound analysed for $C_{20}H_{22}O_2N_2$ and gave the hydroxymethylene compound and ammonia on treatment with warm alkali. On heating above the melting point or on treatment with mineral acids, a new compound ($C_{19}H_{19}O_2N$, m.p. 268°) was formed which on boiling with alcoholic sodium hydroxide afforded a steel-blue sodium salt, identified as the sodium salt of the diketone (VII), $C_{19}H_{17}O_2$ of Ruhemann and Levy (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2549). It therefore appears that the products mentioned above are "ammonia derivatives" of 2-hydroxymethylene-1-indanone or the condensation products thereof. Yet another unidentified product, m.p. 214°, was obtained by the condensation of 2-hydroxymethylene-1-indanone with ethyl 2-aminocrotonate in dry ethanolic solution.

2-Benzylidene-1-indanone (VIII) (Mills and Akers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2475) could not be condensed with ethyl 2-aminocrotonate in boiling acetic acid solution (Petrow *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1949, 2134); the reaction with 2-aminocrotonitrile was, however, brought about in alcoholic sodium ethoxide, affording the 4-azafluorene (IX).

Similarly benzylidene-, *p*-tolylidene- and 1-naphthylidene-acenaphthenone yielded the 7-azafluoranthenes [VI: R = Ph; R = $C_6H_4CH_3$ (*p*) and R = $C_{10}H_7$ (α)]. Benzylidene-acenaphthenone was also condensed with cyanoacetamide to yield 7-azafluoranthenes. The product depended on the condensing agent. For example, with alcoholic sodium ethoxide (X) was the sole product, whereas with diethylamine as a catalyst, the product was (XI).

EXPERIMENTAL*

2-Cyano-3-methyl-4-*o*-hydroxy-4:4-*o*-dihydro-4-azafluorene (I).—Equimolecular quantities of 2-hydroxymethylene-1-indanone and 2-aminocrotonitrile in 10 times their

* All m.p. s are uncorrected.

weight of dry alcohol were allowed to remain at the room temperature for 3 days. The yellowish mass separating was collected. The *hydroxy-azafluorene* (I) was obtained as yellow needles, m.p. 232° from alcohol, yield ca. 30%. (Found: C, 74.5; H, 5.8; N, 12.5. $C_{14}H_{12}ON_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.4; N, 12.5%). With commercial absolute alcohol, the yield was poorer and the compound impure. The condensation may also be brought about in poor yield in dry ethereal solution.

6:7-Dimethoxy derivative of (I) was prepared in a similar way from 2-hydroxy-methylene-5:6-dimethoxy-1-indanone and obtained in yellow crystalline mass, m.p. $300-302^{\circ}$ from alcohol. (Found: C, 67.0; H, 6.0. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires C, 67.6; H, 5.6%).

2-Cyano-3-methyl-4-azafluorene (II).—The foregoing compound (I) was heated for 15 minutes at 280° (metal bath) in vacuum and the product collected on a cold finger. The compound (II) was obtained as colorless needles from alcohol, m.p. $183-84^{\circ}$, yield 40-50%. (Found: C, 82.0; H, 4.8; N, 14.4. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2$ requires C, 81.5; H, 4.9; N, 13.6%).

Ethyl 2-Cyano-3-methyl-4-azafluorene-1-carboxylate (III).—A mixture of ethyl 1-indanone-2-glyoxylate (3 g.) and 2-aminocrotononitrile (1 g.) in dry alcohol (10 c.c.) was allowed to remain at the room temperature for 14 days. The product (III) (0.95 g.) that separated was collected and crystallised from alcohol. It was obtained in long silky needles, m.p. $174-75^{\circ}$. $\lambda_{D_{10}}^{max}$ 2750 Å (log ϵ , 3.01). (Found: C, 73.9; H, 5.2; N, 10.4. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires C, 73.4; H, 5.0; N, 10.1%).

When the condensation was attempted in dry benzene at the room temperature for 4 days, a crop of light yellow needles, m.p. $128-32^{\circ}$, was obtained. All attempts to purify the material by crystallisation resulted in decomposition with the regeneration of the original ester. On boiling with dilute alkali, the compound went into solution with the evolution of ammonia, and the alkaline solution on acidification gave 1-indanone-2-glyoxylic acid, m.p. 218° . (Found: C, 65.1; H, 4.2. $C_{11}H_8O_4$ requires C, 64.7; H, 3.9%). The acid was characterised by the preparation of the *quinoxalin derivative*, obtained in shining orange plates, m.p. 325° , by condensation with *o*-phenylenediamine. (Found: N, 10.8. $C_{17}H_{13}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.1%). The compound dissolved in H_2SO_4 with a rose-red colour.

3-Methyl-4-azafluorene-1:2-dicarboxylic Acid (V).—The foregoing cyano-ester (III: 0.4 g.) was refluxed with aqueous alcoholic NaOH (30%, 6 c.c.) for 18 hours, filtered, alcohol removed in vacuum and the acid precipitated. The acid (0.2 g.) was obtained as a colorless crystalline mass, m.p. $269-71^{\circ}$ from isobutanol. (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{15}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 5.2%).

3-Methyl-4-azafluorene.—An intimate mixture of dry lime and the dicarboxylic acid (V) was cautiously distilled and the reddish oily distillate was converted into the picrate, m.p. 212° , undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen of the picrate.

2-Cyano-3-methyl-4-azafluorene-1-carboxylic Acid (IV).—The cyano-ester (III: 0.2 g.) was added to alcoholic NaOH (0.3 g. in 5 c.c. dry alcohol) and the mixture heated for 2 minutes. The sodium salt separating was collected, dissolved in water

and acidified. The acid was obtained as a gelatinous mass, turning granular on boiling with water. The compound was obtained in prismatic needles from isobutanol, m.p. 274-75°, yield 0.15 g. (Found: N, 11.7. $C_{15}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.2%). On thermal decarboxylation at 290° and collecting the product on a cold finger, 2-cyano-3-methyl-4-azafluorene was obtained, crystallising from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 183-84° (undepressed on admixture with the sample described before). (Found: N, 13.5. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2$ requires N, 13.6%).

Ethyl Acenaphthenone-glyoxylate.—A mixture of acenaphthenone (0.98 g.) and ethyl oxalate in dry alcohol (15 c.c.) was added to alcoholic sodium ethoxide (sodium 0.155 g., alcohol 5 c.c.). The dark mixture was left overnight in a refrigerator and worked up in the usual manner. The ester (0.95 g.) crystallised from alcohol in fine yellow crystalline powder, m.p. 100-101° (Duthie and Plant, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1899, record m.p. 104°). (Found: C, 72.1; H, 4.6. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$: C, 71.6; H, 4.5%).

Ethyl 9-Cyano-8-methyl-7-azafluoranthene-10-carboxylate (VI: R = COOEt).—A mixture of the foregoing oxalyl derivative (0.4 g.) and 2-aminocrotonitrile (0.15 g.) in dry alcohol (5 c.c.) was set aside at the room temperature. The reactants slowly went into solution and the reddish material separating was collected after 14 days and crystallised from dilute alcohol. The ester (0.05 g.) was obtained as short prismatic needles, m.p. 144°. (Found: C, 76.7; H, 4.6. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires C, 76.4; H, 4.5%).

Experiments on the Condensation of Ethyl 2-Aminocrotonate with 2-Hydroxymethylene-1-indanone.—(i). 2-Hydroxymethylene-1-indanone (9.5 g.) was dissolved in ethyl 2-aminocrotonate (25 g.) by warming on the steam-bath with the exclusion of moisture and then set aside at the room temperature for 4 days. The yellow material (2.7 g.) separating was collected and crystallised from benzene in light yellow prisms, m.p. 166°. (Found: C, 74.6, 73.0; H, 6.0, 6.1; N, 8.9, 9.0. $C_{20}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires C, 74.5; H, 7.0; N, 8.7%). *I.R. spectrum*: λ_{max}^{nucl} 3.13s (NH bonded), 5.95 s (cyclic aromatic ketone), 6.07 s, 6.20 s, 6.53 s, 7.70 s and 8.70 μ (:C-NH-C) μ .

The compound imparted a greenish fluorescence to H_2SO_4 and developed a dirty green colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. On warming with dilute alkali the compound went into solution with the evolution of ammonia and the alkaline solution on acidification regenerated the hydroxymethylene compound.

(ii). A mixture of the hydroxymethylene compound (3.2 g.) and ethyl 2-aminocrotonate (2.6 g.) was warmed on the water-bath till a homogeneous solution was obtained and then left at the room temperature for a week. The solid (0.4 g.) was collected and crystallised from *n*-butanol in yellow silky needles, m.p. 268°. This compound is also obtained when the above mentioned compound, m.p. 166°, is treated with dilute HCl or heated at 200° (evolution of ammonia). For analysis, the compound was dried at 80° for 2 hours in vacuum as it retained moisture tenaciously. (Found: C, 73.5; H, 5.2; N, 4.1. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N$ requires C, 73.8; H, 6.2; N, 4.5%).

The compound exhibited a greenish red fluorescence with H_2SO_4 . On boiling the compound with alcoholic NaOH, steel-blue plates of the sodium salt of (VII) were obtained. These were collected, acidified and the solid crystallised from xylene

furnishing (VII), m.p. 233° (undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen). (Found: C, 83.4; H, 4.9. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{14}O_2$: C, 83.2; H, 5.1%).

(iii). Equimolecular solutions of 2-hydroxymethylene-1-indanone and ethyl 2-aminocrotonate in dry alcohol were set aside at the room temperature for 15 days. Very fine yellowish crystals separating were crystallised from aqueous pyridine in light yellow prisms, m.p. 214°. (Found: C, 72.9, 72.8; H, 6.6, 6.2; N, 3.8%).

1-Naphthylidene-acenaphthenone (cf. Graeb and Jequier, *Annalen*, 1896, 290, 204).—To a solution of acenaphthenone (0.5 g.) and 1-naphthaldehyde (0.45 g.) in alcohol (5 c.c.) two drops of NaOH solution (10%) were added. The mixture which darkened immediately was warmed for 15 minutes on the water-bath and left overnight at the room temperature. The compound (0.25 g.) crystallised from aqueous alcohol in thick prisms, m.p. 152-53°. (Found: C, 90.4; H, 4.7. $C_{23}H_{14}O$ requires C, 90.2; H, 4.6%).

p-Tolylidene-acenaphthenone was similarly prepared and obtained in yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 129-30° from aqueous alcohol (yield 75-85%). (Found: C, 89.0; H, 5.6. $C_{20}H_{14}O$ requires C, 88.9; H, 5.2%).

2-Benzylidene-1-indanone was prepared according to Mills and Akers (*loc. cit.*) with the aid of zinc chloride. The main product was different when alkaline catalysts were employed (Kipping, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 66, 498). To a mixture of benzaldehyde (3.2 g.) and 1-indanone (4 g.) a few drops of alcoholic potash were added. The mixture soon acquired a creamy consistency. After agitating with a glass rod for 30 minutes, the mixture was triturated with alcohol, when a granular mass (4.8 g.) appeared. The compound is probably bis-benzylidene-1-indanone. It crystallised from acetic acid in colorless prisms, m.p. 238-40°. (Found: C, 85.8; H, 5.4; M.W., 333. $C_{25}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 85.2; H, 5.7%; M.W., 352). The *infra-red* spectrum showed a strong absorption at 5.95 μ , indicating aromatic carbonyl group.

The *mono-oxime*, obtained on boiling with an excess of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in alcohol, crystallised from acetic acid in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 284°. (Found: C, 82.3; H, 5.6; N, 3.2. $C_{25}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 81.7; H, 5.7; N, 3.8%). *Infra-red spectrum*: λ_{max}^{nujol} 2.9 s (OH), 6.0 s (aromatic ketone), 6.25 s (C=N) μ .

2-Cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-4-azafluorene (IX).—A mixture of 2-benzylidene-1-indanone (0.55 g.), 2-aminocrotonitrile (0.2 g.) and alcoholic sodium ethoxide (Na 0.06 g., alcohol 10 c.c.) was refluxed for 30 minutes, cooled and the *azafluorene* (0.1 g.) collected and crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 199°. (Found: C, 85.0; H, 5.0. $C_{20}H_{14}N_2$ requires C, 85.1; H, 5.0%).

9-Cyano-8-methyl-10-phenyl-7-azafluoranthene.—Benzylidene-acenaphthenone (1.25 g.) was condensed as above with 2-aminocrotonitrile (0.4 g.) in alcoholic sodium ethoxide (Na, 0.12 g. and alcohol, 15 c.c.). The mixture turned violet and within a few minutes a solid (0.75 g.) separated which was collected after 15 minutes. Crystallised from acetic acid, the *azafluoranthene* was obtained as yellowish needles, m.p. 209-10°. (Found: C, 87.2; H, 4.5; N, 8.2. $C_{27}H_{14}N_2$ requires C, 86.8; H, 4.4; N, 8.8%).

9-Cyano-8-methyl-10-p-tolyl-7-azafluoranthene, similarly prepared, crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish prismatic needles, m.p. 251-52°. (Found: C, 87.3; H, 5.1. $C_{24}H_{18}N_2$ requires C, 86.7; H, 4.8%).

8-Cyano-8-methyl-10- α -naphthyl-7-azafluoranthene was obtained as yellow prismatic needles from acetic acid, m.p. 263-65°. (Found: C, 88.7; H, 4.7. $C_{27}H_{18}N_2$ requires C, 88.6; H, 4.3%).

9-Cyano-10-phenyl-8-hydroxy-7-azafluoranthene (X).—Benzylidene-acenaphthenone (0.5 g.) and cyanoacetamide (0.16 g.) were added to sodium ethoxide (Na, 0.06 g. and alcohol, 15 c.c.). The mixture was warmed on the steam-bath for 15 minutes and then left for 3 days at the room temperature. The reddish product (0.25 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in light orange prisms, m.p. >320°. (Found: C, 82.9; H, 4.4. $C_{22}H_{13}ON_2$ requires C, 82.5; H, 3.8%).

8-Keto-9-cyano-10-phenyl-7:8:9:10:10 α :7 α -hexahydro-7-azafluoranthene (XI).—The foregoing condensation was carried out with diethylamine as catalyst. The reaction mixture was left at 40° for 5 days. The compound separated in colorless plates, m.p. >320° from alcohol. (Found: N, 8.3. $C_{22}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.2%).

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